

Blind predictions of polymer pyrolysis and the dual threshold for ignition

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Abstract

In a previous recent paper (Vermesi et al., Comb. Flame, 2016), we investigated the pyrolysis of a polymer under transient irradiation. A model was validated by in-depth temperature measurements, and blind predictions of the mass loss rate were made. The predictions and measurements were then used to establish a dual threshold for ignition based on surface temperature and mass loss rate, which indicates the shortest possible time to ignition. There was a need to verify the validity of the blind predictions of mass loss rate and confirm the previous measurements with additional data. A new set of experiments using Poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) samples were performed to measure mass loss rate and surface temperature. Circular PMMA samples with a diameter of 95.25 mm and a thickness of 30 mm are subjected to parabolic pulses of irradiation ranging from 25 to 45 kW/m² and time to peak between 160 and 480 s. The dual threshold is proven to be valid, and neither thresholds are reached in the cases where ignition does not occur. The surface temperatures show excellent agreement in most cases, with the maximum difference being 10 %. For mass loss rate, the model predicts the peak value with an average error of 58 %, which is acceptable given the experimental difficulty of measuring such small mass loss rates (< 3 g/m²-s). Qualitatively, the mass loss rate measurements serve to validate the blind predictions. Thus, the dual threshold for ignition provides a conservative indication of when ignition will occur.

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1. Introduction

Our recent previous work [1] developed a one dimensional pyrolysis model of PMMA exposed to transient irradiation in the form of parabolic pulses. The model used the open source code Gpyro [2] which simulated the pyrolysis behavior and applied solid phase ignition criteria to determine when ignition occurred, as opposed to simulating the gas-phase ignition itself. The model was validated using a set of experiments conducted in the Fire Propagation Apparatus (FPA). These experiments measured only in-depth temperatures in the PMMA samples, which means that the mass loss rate predictions of the model did not have an experimental counterpart.

The motivation for the addition of this note is to present mass loss rate measurements in comparison to the blind predictions given by the initial model. Also, the concept of dual threshold for ignition (an alternative to the classic ignition criteria [3–6]) that was developed in [1], is further analyzed here. It is important to note that these ignition criteria are certain parameters in the solid phase used to indicate ignition as an alternative to solving the complex phenomena in gas phase, which is where ignition occurs.

The dual threshold for ignition states that the clear PMMA sample will ignite only when the mass loss rate exceeds $3 \text{ g/m}^2\text{-s}$ and the surface temperature is higher than $305 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. This threshold offers a conservative approach to establish the earliest possible time to ignition. Thus, a new set of experiments was devised, using the same material subjected to parabolic pulses of irradiation in order to confirm the dual threshold and to validate the blind predictions.

2. Experiments

The experiments were performed in the FM Global Fire Propagation Apparatus (FPA) using infrared heaters as an external heat source and an ethylene-air pilot flame as an igniter. The transient irradiation was represented by parabolic irradiation curves. The peaks of the parabolic curves range from 25 kW/m^2 to 45 kW/m^2 and the time to peak pulses used are of 160, 260, 320 and 480 s. The experiments were stopped after the irradiation cycle was completed.

Cylindrical samples of clear PMMA in a circular shape with a diameter of 95.25 mm and a thickness of 30 mm were used in the sample holder as presented in Fig. 1. An aluminium block was placed on the back of the sample in order to provide a well-defined bottom boundary that facilitates comparisons with modelling, as shown in Carvel et al. [7]. The thickness of this block is 25.40 mm. The PMMA and aluminium block were insulated on the sides with 3 layers of ceramic fiber blanket with a thickness of 3 mm each. On the bottom, the sample was insulated with 5 layers of ceramic fiber blanket with a thickness of 3 mm each. One experiment was performed for each scenario.

The purpose of these new experiments was to measure the mass loss and the temperatures at the surface and the aluminium block in order to compare them with the blind predictions. Thus these experiments are different in goal from the previous ones in [1], as those measured in-depth temperatures only, without mass loss rates. The same Perspex PMMA was used in both experimental sets. The surface temperature in the new experimental set was measured using an infrared pyrometer, while the temperature in the aluminium block was measured with a wireless thermocouple. These instruments were used to minimize errors on mass loss. The mass loss measurements were obtained using a load cell that was calibrated prior to the tests. The load cell used in the experiments had a range of 0-4500 g, 0.01% full scale accuracy, and 10 mg noise. Mass loss rate data is obtained by taking the derivative of transient load cell measurements and filtering with Savitsky-Golay filters [8]. The pyrometer measurements are corrected for actual emissivity of the surface. The emissivity of the material surface remains bounded between 0.85 and 0.95 for 8-10 m range of pyrometer, approximately; so a material surface emissivity of 0.9 was used to correct pyrometer

temperature, as explained in Chaos et al. [9].

Figure 1: Sketch of the PMMA sample inside the holder with layers and diagnostics

3. The Dual Threshold for Ignition

This new set of experiments serves to further analyze the concept of dual threshold for ignition for mass loss rate and temperature which was established to be at $3 \text{ g/m}^2\text{-s}$ and $305 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [1]. The assumption that MLR and temperature are linked solely through the Arrhenius reaction is simplistic, because they are also linked through the in-depth pyrolysis rate given by the in-depth radiation.

For the scenarios where ignition occurred, the times to ignition are collected in Table 1. The times to ignition from the previous set of experiments are included. The table also presents the earliest predicted time to ignition based on the dual threshold. These are within a range of 8 to 18 % smaller than the recorded time to ignition.

Table 1: Time to ignition measurements (t_{ig}^I for experiments presented here, t_{ig}^{II} for experiments in [1]) and predictions \hat{t}_{ig}

Experiment No.	\dot{q}''_{peak} [kW/m ²]	t_{peak} [s]	t_{ig}^I [s]	t_{ig}^{II} [s]	\hat{t}_{ig} [s]	ε [%]	MLR_{ig} [g/m ² -s]	T_{ig} [°C]
1	30	320	422	450	387	8.3	4.66	339
2	30	480	548	475	449	18.1	6.35	358
3	35	320	359	not conducted	327	8.9	3.17	280
4	40	320	333	300	290	12.9	6.25	320
5	40	480	383	not conducted	350	8.6	4.47	340
6	45	320	296	not conducted	262	11.5	5.42	367

For the scenarios in which ignition did not occur we analyze the maximum mass loss rate and the maximum surface temperature. Table 2 presents these results. The maximum mass loss rates are all below $3 \text{ g/m}^2\text{-s}$. The first peak in mass loss which appears in the experiments (Fig. 3 and 4), but not in the model is of minor importance and can be explained as experimental uncertainty and a modelling issue related to the radiative

absorptivity. For the former, the initial mass of the sample on the load cell (PMMA and aluminium block) is high, therefore the range of the MLR peaks is within the uncertainty range of the load cell. For the latter, the model does not account for the evolution in material radiative absorptivity as a function of temperature and wavelength.

Table 2: MLR and surface temperature comparison between predictions and measurements in the cases where ignition did not occur

No.	\dot{q}''_{peak} [kW/m ²]	t_{peak} [s]	$\text{MLR}_{\text{max,exp}}$ [g/m ² -s]	$\text{MLR}_{\text{max,model}}$ [g/m ² -s]	$\epsilon_{\text{MLR,max}}$ [%]	$T_{\text{max,exp}}$ [°C]	\hat{T}_{max} [°C]	$\epsilon_{T_{\text{max}}}$ [%]
1	30	260	1.48	2.77	87	274	292	3.3
2	25	320	1.17	1.66	41	272	279	1.3
3	35	160	1.37	0.89	35	252	272	3.8
4	40	160	0.80	2.89	72	273	297	4.4

Fig. 2 shows the new experimental data. When neither threshold is exceeded, ignition does not occur. When a single threshold is exceeded, like in the top left and bottom right quarters of the figure, ignition does not occur yet. Only when both MLR and temperature exceed the threshold value does ignition occur.

The scenarios where ignition did not occur are summarized in Table 2. The temperatures are all below the 305 °C, with a maximum difference of 20 °C between the measured and the predicted peak temperature. Thus we think that the dual threshold for ignition of clear PMMA has a general applicability that might be beyond the experimental conditions presented here and in the previous work [1].

Figure 2: Minimum threshold values against experimental mass loss rate and temperature measurements; the lower left part of the plot shows the area where ignition will not occur (i.e. under a mass loss rate of 3g/m²-s and a temperature of 305°C) and the upper right part represents the area where ignition will occur

4. Blind Predictions of Mass Loss Rate

The comparison between this new set of experiments and the predictions are shown in Fig. 3-4. The experiments from [1] are not included in the comparison because direct comparison with the new data is not possible. The previous set measured in-depth temperatures only, which are not measured in the current experiments.

The predicted pre-ignition surface temperatures are very good in all the cases. Quantitatively, the model slightly under-predicts the slope of the heating, with errors in the between 6 % and 10 %, and in some cases over-predicts the surface temperature close to the time to ignition or past the peak temperature in the cases where ignition did not occur with a maximum of 4 %. The largest difference occurs in the scenario presented in Fig. 4(b), where the model under-predicts the temperature by 10 %.

The temperatures in the aluminium block have slightly different shapes, with the model not being able to fully predict the rise in temperature. However, the differences are not so significant, with the largest being 10 %. Therefore, the model always under-predicts the experiments for the temperature in the aluminium block.

It is important to validate the MLR blind predictions in [1] against experimental measurements. In Fig. 3, the mass loss measurements are in good agreement with the blind predictions made in [1]. The shapes of the experimental and modelling curves are very similar, with the model predicting the sudden increase in mass loss to occur faster than in the experiments. In Fig. 4(a), the mass loss rate peak is predicted to occur later than it did in the experiments, with a maximum error of 87 % ($1.29 \text{ g/m}^2\text{-s}$). In Fig. 4(b)-(c), the parabolic shape of the mass loss rate curve is captured correctly, with peak errors of 41 % ($0.49 \text{ g/m}^2\text{-s}$) and 35 % ($0.52 \text{ g/m}^2\text{-s}$).

The excellent agreement between the model and the experiments in the case of surface temperature, as well as the good qualitative agreement of the mass loss rate curves shows that the model successfully reproduced the experiments. This is the first time that mass loss is measured when applying a parabolic pulse of irradiation, and also first comparison in this context to blind predictions.

5. Conclusion

We have produced a new set of experiments of PMMA ignition under transient irradiation conditions in order to confirm the concept of the dual threshold for ignition previously presented in [1] as well as to compare with blind predictions of mass loss rate. The experiments were done on cylindrical PMMA samples which were subjected to a range of parabolic pulses, with peak heat fluxes between 25 and 45 kW/m^2 and times to peak between 160 and 480 s .

The dual threshold for ignition, which gives the shortest time to ignition, is analyzed for all the scenarios. For the samples that ignited, the ignition time predicted by the threshold was between 32 to 100 s lower than the time to ignition recorded during the experiment. In the cases where ignition did not occur, the maximum temperatures and mass loss rates are compared, with none but one scenario not reaching the dual threshold. Therefore, the dual threshold is further proven to be a viable option to estimate the most conservative possibility of ignition.

Surface temperature, bottom boundary temperature and mass loss rate results have been compared to the previous predictions [1]. The temperature predictions show a very good agreement, with similar trends in the experimental and modelling results and a maximum error of 10 %. The mass loss rate results also show good qualitative agreements, with the model predicting the increase in mass loss rate faster than measured

(a) Peak heat flux 30 kW/m^2 , time to peak 320 s

(b) Peak heat flux 30 kW/m^2 , time to peak 480 s

(c) Peak heat flux 35 kW/m^2 , time to peak 320 s

Figure 3: Cases where ignition occurred: comparison between the temperature (surface and aluminium block) and mass loss rate measurements and blind predictions in [1]

in the experiments. Quantitatively, for the cases when ignition did not occur, the average error for mass loss rate is above 50 %, however, this is acceptable considering that the values are small (less than $3 \text{ g/m}^2\text{-s}$).

Figure 4: Cases where ignition did not occur: comparison between the temperature (surface and aluminium block) and mass loss rate measurements and blind predictions

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